

**MAHARASHTRA STATE
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that,

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ABSTRACT

India is an agricultural country where the agriculture sector is the backbone of the economy, contributing to more than 15% of the country's GDP. However, the agriculture sector is facing numerous challenges such as water scarcity, climate change, and low productivity due to outdated farming practices. Therefore, there is a dire need to introduce modern technology in the agriculture sector to enhance its productivity and efficiency. This project presents an IOT Based Smart Agriculture Monitoring System aimed at increasing agricultural productivity by automating and optimizing crop management. The system uses various sensors to monitor environment conditions in real-time. The data collected is processed by a microcontroller and transmitted wirelessly to a web application that provides farmers with visualized information about their crops. The system is designed to be affordable and easy to use, allowing farmers to monitor their crops remotely and take necessary actions to optimize their growth. By providing farmers with real-time data on their crops, the system can help them make informed decisions regarding water and fertilizer usage, pest control, and harvesting times. This, in turn, can lead to increased crop yields, reduced costs, and improved profitability. The project also has future implications, including the integration of machine learning and artificial intelligence technologies to further optimize crop management. With the increasing demand for food production and the need to address the challenges of climate change and food security, this project serves as a promising solution for sustainable agriculture

Smart agriculture is an emerging concept, because IOT sensors are capable of providing information about agriculture fields and then act upon based on the user input. In this System, it is proposed to develop a Smart agriculture System that uses advantages of cutting edge technologies such as ESP 32, IOT and Sensor Network. The system aims at making use of evolving technology i.e. IOT and smart agriculture using automation. Monitoring environmental conditions is the major factor to improve yield of the efficient crops. The feature of this system includes development of a system which can monitor temperature, humidity, moisture in agricultural field through sensors using Esp 32 Microcontroller. The system has a duplex communication link based on a cellular-Internet interface that allows for data inspection and irrigation scheduling to be programmed through Web/android application. Because of its energy autonomy and low cost, the system has the potential to be useful in water limited geographically isolated areas

Modules are as follows:

1. The ESP-32 Will Be Connected To Internet
2. The Controller Collects Data Of Sensors
3. The Controller Sends The Data To Cloud
4. The Data Can Be Viewed Through An Web Based Application
5. If The Soil Moisture Is Greater Buzzer Will Rang

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CHAPTER NO. 1

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is a major source of income for India's largest population and a major contributor to the Indian economy. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a technology that allows the use of mobile devices to control the operation of devices. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a kind of network technology that receives and exchanges information from various sensors and is best connected to the Internet. This is done by higher-level communication devices such as Wi-Fi modules. The data processed by the sensor is converted into meaningful data and sent to the user. Users can view data using portable devices such as mobile phones or tablets. The project helps farmers efficiently irrigate their fields with an automated soil moisture-based irrigation system. The proposed system is designed to overcome unnecessary water runoff to farmland. Temperature, Humidity, and soil moisture readings are continuously monitored by the Temperature, Humidity, and Humidity Sensor and sent to a designated mobile phone. The Cloud things peak continuously collects data from assigned API address key When the soil moisture value exceeds a certain limit, a relay connected to the ESP32 microcontroller controls the automation of the irrigation system using the PUMP

CHAPTER NO 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

While making this project, we referred to several books, technical magazines, websites and visited some technical exhibitions. We have listed these references below.

Websites:

1. www.circuitstoday.com
2. www.howstuffworks.com
3. www.societyofrobots.com
4. www.electricstuff.co.uk

Sr.no	Name of Author And Year	Paper Title	Paper Is About	Result	Conclusion/Remarks
1	Swaraj C M, K M Sowmyashree (2020)	IoT based Smart Agriculture Monitoring and Irrigation System	The design also helps in decreasing global warming to a grand period.	Inventing in the specialization where the crops are costly are monitored and all the climatic requirements are well preserved essential	The innate habit of plants is controlled indirectly. The plants can also be saved from fire by use. This in turn helps in decreasing crop obliteration. Thereby, the ecological equilibrium is preserved
2.	Yick, Jennifer, Biswanath Mukherjee, and Dipak Ghosal (2008)	Wireless sensor network survey." Computer networks	WSN applications such as communication architectures, security, and management.	Close the gap between technology and application.	Studied WSN applications such as communication architectures, security, and management between technology and application
3.	Tubaishat, M., & Madria, S. (2003)	Sensor networks: an overview	Sensor networks should sustain network connectivity actually if some of their sensors are transferred.	Sensors are their ability to maintain connectivity in case of movement. As these sensors are very tiny, they are vulnerable to being accidentally moved	Data produced by the sensors usually have to be routed through several intermediate nodes to reach their destination
4.	Yang, L. D. (2011)	Implementation of a wireless sensor network with EZ430-RF2500 development tools and MSP430FG461 8/F2013 experimenter	A wireless sensor network is implemented with eZ430RF2500 wireless development	It can be proved that the temperature displayed on the PC is one period ago for the slave boards and two	Every device has to be programmed to sense the temperature immediately after querying.

		boards from Texas instruments.	tools and MSP430FG46 18/F2013 experimenter boards, ultralowpower, and low-cost devices from Texas Instrument	periods ago for the eZ430RF2500 nodes each time when the display is refreshed.	
5.	Lozano, C., & Rodriguez, O. (2011)	Design of forest fire early detection system using wireless sensor networks. Electronics and Electrical Engineering	Prevention of forest fires using wireless sensor networks.	Protection of nature reserves from forest fires is possible with this type of network.	When deploying network equipment is set correctly selected all measures are and generates alarms when the temperature exceeds the threshold.
6	Sepaskhah, A. R., & Ahmadi, S. H. (2012)	A review on partial rootzone drying irrigation	Wide applications of partial rootzone drying irrigation (PRD) on diverse plant species.	PRD is successful alternative irrigation compared to FI that can save irrigation water up to approximately 50% without significant yield loss, while may improve the yield quality	The amount of saved irrigation water and improved WP strongly depends on the crop, soil, and site Specifications
7	Galgalikar, M. M. (2010)	Real-time automization of agricultural environment for social modernization of Indian agricultural system	ARM7 and GSM are concentrating on automizing the irrigation scheme for the social interest of the Indian farming technique	The system not only saves energy consumption significantly but also reduces a large number of input on the human and material resources in the management.	Enhances the system's flexibility, small size, low cost, and good effectiveness, so it is easy to install and migrate.

8	Nikolidakis, S. A., Kandris, D., Vergados, D. D., & Douligeris, C. (2015).	Energy efficient automated control of irrigation in agriculture by using wireless sensor networks.	Automatic irrigation managing with an Avant book routing protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), called ECHERP (Equalized Cluster Head Election Routing Protocol).	Raised to evaluate the impact of the area features on the amount of water needed for irrigation.	Efficient irrigation ideals along with energy-efficient utilization of WSNs display to be a very favorable and adequate application of industrialization in farming.
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1.Sushanth, and S. Sujatha -This paper provide , to develop a smart agriculture system using IoT. Smart agriculture is a unique concept in which IoT sensors offer information about agricultural regions and then act on it in response to human input. The purpose of this study is to develop a smart agricultural system that makes use of cutting-edge technologies such as wireless sensor networks, the Internet of Things, and ESP32. Through automation, the research takes advantage of emerging technologies such as smart agriculture and the Internet of Things (IoT). Monitoring environmental variables can enhance crop efficiency. The purpose of this study is to develop a system that can use sensors to analyze temperature, humidity, wetness, and even the movement of animals in agricultural areas that could harm crops. If an error happens, the system will send an SMS message to the farmer's smartphone as well as a notification to the app developed for it through Wi- Fi/3G/4G. An Android app can be used to inspect and change the watering schedule of the system's duplex communication channel, which is based on a cellular Internet interface. Because of its energy

2.Mahmoud Abbasi, Mohammad Hossein Yaghmaee, Fereshteh Rahnama- In this survey, challenges and applications in agriculture examined. Precision agriculture is the use of information technology in agriculture as a result of increased food consumption, customer demand for high-quality food, and agricultural environmental effects. The Internet of Things (IOT) is a rapidly evolving technology that has various advantages for agriculture. Because of the varied and amount of data collected by IoT sensors, cloud computing is critical to the future of internet of things (IoT) agricultural applications. Microcontrollers will simultaneously enhance the capabilities of the internet of things (IoT). The IOT applications in agriculture, as well as the research trend, concepts, and basic IOT components, are assessed in this paper. First, an appraisal of the number of publications published in this field. Second, an overview of IOT definition and architecture, covering levels. The main difficulties in IOT and precision agriculture (PA) are then addressed, followed by a comparison of some IOT-related technologies.

3.Junhu Ruan, Yan Shi, Felix Tung Sun Chan In this paper , survey on bring out emerging trends in both applied IoT techniques and agriculture is carried out. As a result of the Internet of Things (IoT) age, our modern world has experienced a revolution. Precision agriculture will eventually become a practical, cheap, and sustainable technique of increasing agricultural yields and quality with the ongoing deployment of IoT methods in agriculture. In order to facilitate implementation, we use records from 3168 documents and their 100,205 references in Web of Science to build a visualization assessment of the farm IoT literature over the preceding ten years. The dynamics of research fronts and intellectual bases reveal emerging trends in both applied IoT technology and agriculturally linked areas of concern. The amount of contributions in cooperative networks is used to identify outstanding nations, institutions, and authors. Furthermore, from 2009 to 2018, the citation networks identified notable papers and authors, indicating hot topics and trends in the farm IoT literature. We also make future recommendations as part of the review, such as building infrastructure for the Internet of Things in agriculture, data security and sharing, sustainable energy solutions, economic analysis and operation management in the Internet of Things in agriculture, and IoT-based financing and e-business

models. These findings will be useful to researchers and industry professionals in their future efforts to develop IoT-based precision agriculture.

4. Mohamed Amine Ferrag, Lei Shu It carried out challenges on security and privacy issues in the field of green IoT based agriculture. This paper discusses security and privacy research problems in the context of IoT-based green agriculture. We begin by summarizing current smart agriculture surveys and outlining a four-tier green IoT-based farm architecture. The threat models against IoT-based green agriculture are then classified into five categories, with intrusions into authentication, confidentiality, availability, and integrity aspects being included in each. Furthermore, we provide a taxonomy and a side-by-side comparison of the most sophisticated methods to secure and privacy-preserving IoT technologies, as well as research, as well as the security objectives on which the research has been focused

5. Vippon Preet Kour, Sakshi Arora It contribute towards recent IoT technologies in agriculture sector along with development of hardware and software systems. Because of population growth, the agricultural industry's need has expanded dramatically. With the advancement of technology, this decade has seen a shift from traditional to cutting-edge ways. Because of the Internet of Things (IoT), the agriculture sector has altered in terms of both quality and quantity. The farms' real-time monitoring and species hybridization enabled resource optimization. Scientists, research groups, academics, and the majority of governments worldwide are moving towards the practice and execution of joint efforts in order to explore the potential of this sector to serve humanity. The IT industry is competing to provide even better solutions. Combining IoT with cloud computing, big data analytics, and wireless sensor networks can provide you ample room to predict, process, and analyze events while also improving your real-time operations. The notion of device heterogeneity and interoperability is also presenting new possibilities in this domain by delivering adaptive, scalable, and durable techniques and models. As a result, together with the growth of hardware and software systems, this study contributes to modern IoT technologies in the agriculture business. The projects and businesses developed by the public and private sectors around the world to provide smart and sustainable precision agriculture solutions are also discussed. A brief assessment of the current situation, applications, research potential, restrictions, and future aspects is provided. A precision agriculture framework based on IoT concepts is also proposed in this research.

6. Ashok Kumar Das, Anusha Vangala, Neeraj Kumar It provide information security using blockchain technology. Agriculture is vital to humanity's survival since it encompasses manufacturing, security, traceability, and long term resource management. Because resources are rapidly running out, developing innovative techniques to promote agricultural subsistence is vital. The expansion of the Internet of Things (IoT) and blockchain technology, two fast growing domains, have the potential to improve the current state of the food chain. This report does a thorough literature review to analyze the most recent advancements in systems that leverage blockchain technology to ensure information security. Following the identification of smart agriculture's main requirements, a general blockchain-based security architecture has been provided. The plans under consideration have been assessed. A thorough comparison analysis revealed the limitations of previous studies. A thorough examination of the literature has also aided in identifying new topics for future artificial intelligence

7. Shrihari M In this survey, automate production of crops and stop intrusion using deep learning is carried out. Irrigation is a fundamental problem that scientists and farmers encounter while attempting to automate agricultural production; this concept has been around since the early 1990s. Irrigation is a dynamic system that is heavily influenced by external events. The method discussed in this article employs a specially constructed mathematical model to manage data from wireless sensors on Google Cloud in order to create a smart system. a design that can be scaled up to big farms and is IoT enabled. According to Holistic Agricultural Studies, 35 have been harmed by both animals and humans. This intelligent system employs tensor flow and deep learning neural networks to identify animals based on their hazard level as well as unauthorized human visitors to the farm and instantly notify the farmer. The device comes with an Android app that allows for remote access and live video streaming surveillance.

Chapter No 3 Scope of Project

The scope of an IoT based smart agriculture monitoring system project can include several aspects such as hardware and software development, system design, testing, and validation, among others. The specific scope of the project may depend on the objectives, requirements, and resources available.

Some potential areas of scope for an IoT Based Smart Agriculture Monitoring System project could include:

- With the help of sensors, the labor need will decrease
- The sensor allows precisely measure the moisture level of soil
- The temperature sensor detects the temperature level precisely and accurately Than the manual process
- This may involve using statistical methods and other analytical tools to process the data collected by the system and generate useful insights
- This may involve creating a user-friendly interface that allows farmers to easily access and interpret the data collected by the system

Application Areas

- a. Those places where temperature suddenly vary with the help of this we can monitor temperature easily.
- b. Crops where we can't monitor the different required parameters of crops.
- c. All those areas where industrial toxic gases effect on crops health
- d. Areas where labor can't go and unable to access, we can easily monitor crop variable on real-time.

Chapter No 4 Project Development Methodology

Fig 1 - Evaluation

Project implementation method includes following points.

- └ Design of System such that there are total one mesh containing two nodes present and each node consist of sensors unit that receives data from sensors unit and after it is linked with micro-controller to convert this analogue data in to the digital and send it to NODE MCU ESP8266 module from where it will be communicated to main controller.
- └ All sensors and NODE MCU ESP8266 module are connected with microcontroller and the collected data of these sensors are send to Thingspeak through NOD MCU ESP8266. These sensors collect data according to their specialty.
- └ Micro-controller is connected with NODE MCU ESP8266 and in this case micro-controller received all the data of sensors and send toward NODE MCU ESP8266 and then NODE MCU ESP8266 will communicate IoT Platform

Chapter No 5

Details of Design ,Working and process

The Internet of things (IoT) is the network of everyday objects — physical things embedded with electronics, software, sensors, and connectivity enabling data exchange. Basically, a little networked computer is attached to a thing, allowing information exchange to and from that thing. Be it lightbulbs, toasters, refrigerators, flower pots, watches, fans, planes, trains, automobiles, or anything else around you, a little networked computer can be combined with it to accept input (especially object control) or to gather and generate informational output (typically object status or other sensory data). This means computers will be permeating everything around us — ubiquitous embedded computing devices, uniquely identifiable, interconnected across the Internet. Because of low-cost, networkable microcontroller modules, the Internet of things is really starting to take off.

In this project, it is necessary to continuously store the data with real time. monitoring system is used in such places. This device measures the data and displays it with real time and keeps storing it in on cloud. The data are various parameters of sensors If consider this varying input has to be studied, we can do it by knowing the different readings at different time period with the help of the data sent to the cloud. This data gets stored, plotted, imported, exported with the help of online API named Thingspeak.com or if you are using google firebase then depends on project requirement we can change the GUI of Android application.

This system even monitors whether the input is within specific limits or else there is an alarm warning for it at the Transmitter. This information will be sent to cloud with help of Wi-Fi module i.e ESP32 There will be specific limits set inside the microcontroller for the data. Consider if the data goes above this limits, the buzzer will make noise and the range of the data will be shown as out on the CLOUD

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 2 -block diagram of working of system with iot cloud

Block Diagram Description:

Analog Sensors

There are different types of sensors that produce continuous analog output signal and these sensors are considered as analog sensors. This continuous output signal produced by the analog sensors is proportional to the measured. There are various types of analog sensors; practical examples of various types of analog sensors are as follows: accelerometers, pressure sensors, light sensors, sound sensors, temperature sensors, and so on.

In our project we are using sensor as

Digital Sensor:

As its name implies, **Digital Sensors** produce a discrete digital output signals or voltages that are a digital representation of the quantity being measured. Digital sensors produce a Binary output signal in the form of a logic “1” or a logic “0”, (“ON” or “OFF”). This means then that a digital signal only produces discrete (non-continuous) values which may be outputted as a single “bit”, (serial transmission) or by combining the bits to produce a single “byte” output (parallel transmission).

his

Capacitive soil moisture sensor measures soil moisture levels by capacitive sensing rather than resistive sensing like other sensors on the market. It is made of corrosion-resistant material which gives it excellent service life. Insert it into the soil around your plants and impress your friends with real-time soil moisture data!

Operating Voltage	3.3 ~ 5.5 VDC
Output Voltage	0 ~ 3.0VDC
Operating Current	5mA
Interface	PH2.54-3P
Dimensions mm(LxWxH)	98 × 23 × 4
Weight (g):	15
Shipping Weight	0.018 kg
Shipping Dimensions	12 × 4 × 1 cm

Table 1 – Specifications Of Soil Moisture Sensor

This module includes an onboard voltage regulator which gives it an operating voltage range of **3.3 ~ 5.5V**. It is perfect for low-voltage **MCUs**, both **3.3V**, and **5V**. For compatibility with ESP32

This soil moisture sensor is compatible with our **3-pin “Gravity”** interface, which we can connect to the **Gravity I/O expansion shield**. Applications:

1. Garden plants
2. Moisture detection
3. Intelligent agriculture

Figure 3- Capacitive Type Soil Moisture Sensor

Temperature and Humidity Sensor DHT-11

Figure 4: Temperature and Humidity Sensor DHT-11

The DHT11 is a basic, ultra low-cost digital temperature and humidity sensor. It uses a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor to measure the surrounding air and spits out a digital signal on the data pin (no analog input pins needed). It's fairly simple to use but requires careful timing to grab data. The only real downside of this sensor is you can only get new data from it once every 2 seconds, so when using our library, sensor readings can be up to 2 seconds old. Technical Details

- Low cost
- 3 to 5V power and I/O
- 2.5mA max current use during conversion (while requesting data)
- Good for 20-80% humidity readings with 5% accuracy
- Good for 0-50°C temperature readings $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ accuracy
- No more than 1 Hz sampling rate (once every second)
- Body size 15.5mm x 12mm x 5.5mm
- 4 pins with 0.1" spacing

Sr. No	Pins	Connection
1	Vcc	+3.3 V – 5.5 V (Input High)
2	GND	Ground (LOW)
3	Data Pin	Connected with ESP32

Table 2: Pin Configuration of DHT11

Where to use DHT11 Sensors

The **DHT11** is a commonly used **Temperature and humidity sensor**. The sensor comes with a dedicated NTC to measure temperature and an 8-bit microcontroller to output the values of temperature and humidity as serial data. The sensor is also factory calibrated and hence easy to interface with other microcontrollers.

The sensor can measure temperature from 0°C to 50°C and humidity from 20% to 90% with an accuracy of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $\pm 1\%$. So if you are looking to measure in this range then this sensor might be the right choice for you.

How to use DHT11 Sensor

The DHT11 Sensor is factory calibrated and outputs serial data and hence it is highly easy to set it up. The connection diagram for this sensor is shown below.

Figure 5- Block Diagram Of DHT-11 Sensor Connection

As you can see the data pin is connected to an I/O pin of the MCU and a 5K pull-up resistor is used. This data pin outputs the value of both temperature and humidity as serial data. If you are trying to interface DHT11 with ESP32 then there are ready-made libraries for it which will give you a quick start.

If you are trying to interface it with some other MCU, then the datasheet given below will come in handy. The output given out by the data pin will be in the order of 8bit humidity integer data + 8bit the Humidity decimal data +8 bit temperature integer data + 8bit fractional temperature data +8 bit parity bit. To request the DHT11 module to send these data the I/O pin has to be momentarily made low and then held high as shown in the timing diagram below

Figure 6 – Signal Wave Form Of DHT-11 Sensor

The duration of each host signal is explained in the DHT11 datasheet, with neat steps and illustrative timing diagrams. Compared to the DHT22, this sensor is less precise, less accurate, and works in a smaller range of temperature/humidity, but its smaller and less expensive

ESP32-

Figure 7 – ESP32 Board

ESP32 is a chip that provides Wi-Fi and (in some models) Bluetooth connectivity for embedded devices – in other words, for IoT devices. While ESP32 is technically just the chip, the modules and development boards that contain this chip are often also referred to as “ESP32” by the manufacturer.

The original ESP32 chip had a single core Tensilica Xtensa LX6 microprocessor. The processor had a clock rate of over 240 MHz, which made for a relatively high data processing speed.

More recently, new models were added, including the ESP32-C and -S series, which include both single and dual core variations. These two series also rely on a Risc-V CPU model instead of Xtensa. Risc-V is similar to the ARM architecture, which is well-supported and well-known, but Risc-V is open source and easy to use. Specifically, Risc-V and ARM have good support from GNU compilers, while the Xtensa needed extra support and development to work with the compilers.

The newer models are available with combined Wi-Fi and Bluetooth connectivity, or just Wi-Fi connectivity. There are several different chip models available, including:

ESP32-D0WDQ6 (and ESP32D0WD)

ESP32-D2WD

ESP32-S0WD

System in package (SiP) – ESP32-PICO-D4

ESP32 S series

ESP32-C series

ESP32-H series

The ESP32 is most commonly used for mobile devices, wearable tech, and IoT applications, such as Nabto Edge. Moreover, since Mongoose OS introduced an ESP32 IoT Starter Kit, the ESP32 has gained a reputation as the ultimate chip for hobbyists and IoT developers. It’s suitable for commercial IoT, and its capabilities and resources have grown impressively over the past four years.

ESP32 features and specifications

Here’s a high-level summary of the features and specifications of the ESP32:

ESP-32	DESCRIPTION
Core	2
Architecture	32 bits
Clock	Tensilica Xtensa LX106 160-240MHz

WiFi	IEEE802.11 b/g/n
Bluetooth	Yes - classic & BLE
RAM	520KB
Flash	External QSPI - 16MB
GPIO	22
DAC	2
ADC	18
Interfaces	SPI-I2C-UART-I2S-CAN

Table 3 – ESP 32 Specifications

And here's a more detailed summary:

Processors – The ESP32 uses a Tensilica Xtensa 32-bit LX6 microprocessor. This typically relies on a dual core architecture, with the exception of one module, the ESP32-S0WD, which uses a single-core system. The clock frequency reaches up to 240MHz and it performs up to 600 DMIPS (Dhrystone millions of instructions per second). Moreover, its low power consumption allows for analog to digital conversions as well as computation and level thresholds, even while the chip is in deep sleep mode.

Wireless connectivity – The ESP32 enables connectivity to integrated Wi-Fi through the 802.11 b/g/n/e/i/. Moreover, Bluetooth connectivity is made possible with the v4.2 BR/EDR, and the series also features Bluetooth low energy (BLE).

Memory – Internal memory for the ESP32 is as follows. ROM: 448 KB (for booting/core functions), SRAM: 520 KB (for data/instructions), RTC fast SRAM: 8 KB (for data storage/main CPU during boot from sleep mode), RTC slow SRAM: 8 KB (for co-processor access during sleep mode), and

eFuse: 1 KiBit (256 bits used for the system (MAC address and chip configuration) and 768 bits reserved for customer applications).

Moreover, some of the ESP32 chips, including the ESP32-D2WD and ESP32-PICO-D4, have internally connected flash. See the respective internal flash memory for each chip in the ESP32 Chips section.

External flash and SRAM – ESP32 supports up to four 16 MB external QSPI flashes and SRAMs with hardware encryption based on AES to protect developers' programs and data. It accesses the external QSPI flash and SRAM through high-speed caches.

Security – The ESP32 supports all IEEE 802.11 standard security features, including WPA, WPA/WPA2 and WAPI. Moreover, ESP32 has a secure boot and flash encryption.

ESP32 functions

ESP32 has many applications when it comes to IoT. Here are just some of the IoT functions the chip is used for:

Networking: The module's Wi-Fi antenna and dual core enables embedded devices to connect to routers and transmit data.

Data processing: Includes processing basic inputs from analog and digital sensors to far more complex calculations with an RTOS or non-OS software development kit (SDK). A non-OS SDK refers to one that is designed to run directly on the chip without a full operating system supporting it.

P2P connectivity: Creates direct communication between different ESPs and other devices using IoT P2P connectivity.

- Web server: Provides access to pages written in HTML or development languages.
- ESP32 Applications
- The ESP32 modules are commonly found in the following IoT devices:
- Smart industrial devices, including programmable logic controllers (PLCs)
- Smart medical devices, including wearable health monitors
- Smart energy devices, including HVAC and thermostats
- Smart security devices, including surveillance cameras and smart locks
- Chip versus modules versus development boards

The ESP32 is just the name of the chip. Device manufacturers and developers have three different format choices, and the decision of which one to go with will depend on their individual circumstances:

ESP32 chip: This is the bare-bones chip that is manufactured by Espressif. It comes unshielded, meaning there's no protective casing, and it can't be attached to a module or board without soldering. Therefore, most device manufacturers do not purchase just the chip, as this will add an additional layer of complexity to the production process.

ESP32 modules: These are surface mountable modules that contain the chip. The modules are essentially small electrical components that can be attached to a circuit board. The benefit here is that you can easily mount these modules onto an MCU board. The chip is also usually shielded and pre-approved by the FCC, which means device manufacturers do not need to worry about adding additional steps to the production process to achieve FCC compliance regarding Wi-Fi shielding.

ESP32 development boards: These are IoT MCU development boards that have the modules containing the ESP32 chip preinstalled. They are used by hobbyists, device manufacturers and developers to test and prototype IoT devices before entering mass production. There is a wide variety of makes and models of ESP32 development boards, produced by different manufacturers. Here are some important specs to consider when choosing a suitable IoT ESP32 development board:

- GPIO pins
- ADC pins
- Wi-Fi antennas
- LEDs
- Shielding*
- Flash memory

*Many international markets require shielded Wi-Fi devices, as Wi-Fi produces a lot of radio frequency interference (RFI), and shielding minimizes this interference. This should, therefore, be a key consideration for all developers and embedded device manufacturers.

DC PUMP:

Figure 8 – DC Pump

Micro Submersible Water Pump DC 3V-5V, can be easily integrate to your water system project. The water pump works using water suction method which drain the water through its inlet and released it through the outlet. You can use the water pump as exhaust system for your aquarium and controlled water flow fountain.

SPECIFICATION:

- Input Voltage: DC 3V-5V
- Flow Rate: 1.2-1.6 L/min
- Operation Temperature: 80 Deg.C
- Operating Current: 0.1-0.2A
- Suction Distance: 0.8 meter (Max)
- Outside diameter of water outlet: 7.5mm
- Inside diameter of water outlet: 5.0 mm
- Diameter of water Inlet : 5.0 mm
- Wire Length: 200 mm
- Size: 45 x 30 x 25 mm
- Weight: 30g

RELAY

A relay is an electrical switch that opens and closes under the control of another electrical circuit. In the original form, the switch is operated by an electromagnet to open or close one or many sets of contacts. It was invented by Joseph Henry in 1835. Because a relay is able to control an output circuit of higher power than the input circuit, it can be considered to be, in a broad sense, a form of an electrical amplifier. In this these projects we can use electromagnetic relay.

Figure 9 - Relay

Power supply:

Figure 10 - . 2576 Voltage Regulator IC

Voltage sources in a circuit may have fluctuations resulting in not providing fixed voltage outputs. A voltage regulator IC maintains the output voltage at a constant value. 2576 Voltage Regulator, a member of

of SWITCHING voltage regulators used to maintain such fluctuations, is a popular voltage regulator integrated circuit (IC). The xx in 78xx indicates the output voltage it provides. 2576 IC provides +5 volts regulated power supply with provisions to add a heat sink. so for working we need power supply of 5v if we use motor or relay then we need 12v power supply.

The LM2576 series of regulators are monolithic integrated circuits that provide all the active functions for a step-down (buck) switching regulator, capable of driving 3-A load with excellent line and load regulation. These devices are available in fixed output voltages of 3.3 V, 5 V, 12 V, 15 V, and an adjustable output version

LM2576 Voltage regulator are designed to minimize the number of external components to simplify the power supply design. Standard series of inductors optimized for use with the LM2576 voltage regulator are offered by several different inductor manufacturers.

Since the LM2576 converter IC is a switch-mode power supply, its efficiency is significantly higher in comparison with popular three-terminal linear regulators, especially with higher input voltages. In many cases, the power dissipated is so low that no heat sink is required or its size could be reduced dramatically. A standard series of inductors optimized for use with the LM2576 are available from several different manufacturers. This feature greatly simplifies the design of switch-mode power supplies. The LM2576 adjustable voltage regulator features include a guaranteed $\pm 4\%$ tolerance on output voltage within specified input voltages and output load conditions, and $\pm 10\%$ on the oscillator frequency ($\pm 2\%$ over 0°C to 125°C). External shutdown is included, featuring 80 μA (typical) standby current. The output switch includes cycle-by-cycle current limiting, as well as thermal shutdown for full protection under fault conditions.

We have various types of Voltage Regulator IC's. Check our complete collection of Voltage Regulator IC's.

Features of LM2576 adjustable Voltage Regulator

- Output Voltage ($V_{in} = 12\text{ V}$, $I_{Load} = 0.5\text{ A}$, $T_J = 25^\circ\text{C}$) V_{out} Min:1.23 Volts; Max:37 Volts
- Efficiency ($V_{in} = 15\text{ V}$, $I_{Load} = 3.0\text{ A}$) $\eta=77\%$
- Guaranteed 3.0 A Output Current
- Wide Input Voltage Range
- Requires Only 4 External Components
- 52 kHz Fixed Frequency Internal Oscillator
- TTL Shutdown Capability, Low Power Standby Mode
- High Efficiency
- Uses Readily Available Standard Inductors
- Thermal Shutdown and Current Limit Protection
- Moisture Sensitivity Level (MSL) Equals 1
- Pb-Free Packages are Available

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM:

Figure 11- Connection Diagram Of Whole System

Power Requirement

As the operating voltage range of ESP32 is 3V to 3.6V, the board comes with a LDO voltage regulator to keep the voltage steady at 3.3V. It can reliably supply up to 600mA, which should be more than enough when ESP32 pulls as much as 80mA during RF transmissions. The output of the regulator is also broken out to one of the sides of the board and labelled as 3V3. This pin can be used to supply power to external components.

Peripherals and I/O

The ESP32 has total 38 GPIO pins broken out to the pin headers on both sides of the development board.

These pins can be assigned to all sorts of peripheral duties, including:

- ADC channel – A 10-bit ADC channel.
- UART interface – UART interface is used to load code serially.
- PWM outputs – PWM pins for dimming LEDs or controlling motors.
- SPI, I2C & I2S interface – SPI and I2C interface to hook up all sorts of sensors and peripherals.
- I2S interface – I2S interface if you want to add sound to your project.

The ESP32 is a \$4 (up to \$10) Wi-Fi module. It allows you to control inputs and outputs as you would do with an ESP32, but it comes with Wi-Fi.

So, it is great for internet of things applications.

This is a 5V 3A Switching Regulator circuit using LM2576-5.0. It is simple switching power supply 3A step down regulator for power digital circuits.

Sometimes, we need to work on the car or travel outside the area. The without wires internet ADSL. When using the Internet was using 4G air cards and distributed to the Internet via wireless with “mobile wireless router”.

It requires a power supply of 5V 2A. Because it is a digital circuit which uses a 10-watts high power.

Figure 12 – Diagram Of Switching Regulator Circuit

When it comes to using in cars. We can use power from the cigarette lighter of a car. But have the voltage 12 volts, so it must reduce the voltage down to 5 volts current is 2 amperes. We have a lot of choices. When before I use the transistor and IC-7805 for this job. However, when considered with caution. To its low performance. have high temperature and large, as the identity of the generally linear ICs. This work, we try to do the switching IC.

IC-LM2576-5.0. (DC to DC step down voltage regulator) It is a very interesting number. It maintains a constant voltage of approximately 5 volts and current 3A. Compatible with the device easily. On the manufacturer’s manual. I smile with ease. It is very easy to use. as Figure 1. Will see that there are only four more devices only are C1-100uF, D1-1N5822, L1-100uH, C2-1000uF. The input voltage levels are

7volts to 40volts. My favorite feature is the runs with high frequency. IC is not hot. It can hold a small cooler. And Used continuously for a long time.

In addition we also can change the number of ICs. To change the voltage was volts output many the level be LM2576-3.3 (3.3Vdc output), LM2576-5.0 (5Vdc output), LM2576-12 (12Vdc output), LM2576-15 (15Vdc output),LM2576-ADJ (1.23Vdc to 37Vdc output) ,

ESP32 Buzzer Circuit Diagram

Buzzer:

The Buzzer connected to an ESP32 is an output device that produces audible sounds or tones. It can be used to provide audio feedback to the user or to alert the user of a specific event.

In the context of a gas sensor, the buzzer can be used to alert the user when a certain level of gas concentration is detected. For example, if the gas sensor is detecting a dangerous level of gas, the ESP32 can activate the buzzer to produce a loud sound to alert the user to take appropriate action, such as turning off the gas supply or evacuating the area.

Figure 13: Buzzer

The circuit shown here uses a NPN transistor to connect the buzzer to the ESP32. The transistor allows the buzzer to be powered from a different voltage to the ESP32. Any NPN transistor that can handle the current drawn by the buzzer can be used.

With a PN2222 and 2k2 base resistor, the circuit can be used to operate a buzzer that draws up to about 200mA.

Figure 14 – Buzzer Circuit Diagram

Although the circuit shows the buzzer being powered from 12V, the circuit allows any buzzer that operates from about 5V to around 24V to be used.

When the external power supply (12V in the circuit diagram) is connected, the GND or 0V of the power supply must be connected to the GND of the ESP32.

So the above circuit means that the connections must be made as follows:

Figure 15- The power supply powering the buzzer in this circuit is a 12V battery.

Software Requirement:

ESP32 Programming Software

ESP32 IDE is a special software running on your system that allows you to write sketches (synonym for **program** in **ESP32** language) for different **ESP32** boards. The **ESP32 programming** language is based on a very simple hardware **programming** language called processing, which is similar to the C language

The ESP32 integrated development environment (IDE) is a cross-platform application (for Windows, macOS, Linux) that is written in the programming language Java. It is used to write and upload programs to ESP32 compatible boards, but also, with the help of 3rd party cores, other vendor development boards.

The source code for the IDE is released under the GNU General Public License, version 2. The ESP32 IDE supports the languages C and C++ using special rules of code structuring. The ESP32 IDE supplies a software library from the Wiring project, which provides many common input and output procedures. Userwritten code only requires two basic functions, for starting the sketch and the main program loop, that are compiled and linked with a program stub main() into an executable cyclic executive program with the GNU toolchain, also included with the IDE distribution.[5] The ESP32 IDE employs the program avrdude to convert the executable code into a text file in hexadecimal encoding that is loaded into the ESP32 board by a loader program in the board's firmware

The ESP32 Integrated Development Environment - or ESP32 Software (IDE) - contains a text editor for writing code, a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions and a series of menus. It connects to the ESP32 and Genuino hardware to upload programs and communicate with them.

Writing Sketches

Programs written using ESP32 Software (IDE) are called sketches. These sketches are written in the text editor and are saved with the file extension. ino. The editor has features for cutting/pasting and for searching/replacing text. The message area gives feedback while saving and exporting and also displays errors. The console displays text output by the ESP32 Software (IDE), including complete error messages and other information. The bottom righthand corner of the window displays the configured board and serial port. The toolbar buttons allow you to verify and upload programs, create, open, and save sketches, and open the serial monitor.

NB: Versions of the ESP32 Software (IDE) prior to 1.0 saved sketches with the extension .pde. It is possible to open these files with version 1.0, you will be prompted to save the sketch with the .ino extension on save.

Verify

Checks your code for errors compiling it.

Upload

Compiles your code and uploads it to the configured board. See uploading below for details.

Note: If you are using an external programmer with your board, you can hold down the "shift" key on your computer when using this icon. The text will change to "Upload using Programmer"

New

Creates a new sketch.

Open

Presents a menu of all the sketches in your sketchbook. Clicking one will open it within the current window overwriting its content.

Note: due to a bug in Java, this menu doesn't scroll; if you need to open a sketch late in the list, use the File | Sketchbook menu instead.

Save

Saves your sketch.

Serial Monitor

Opens the serial monitor.

Additional commands are found within the five menus: File, Edit, Sketch, Tools, Help. The menus are context sensitive, which means only those items relevant to the work currently being carried out are available.

File

New

Creates a new instance of the editor, with the bare minimum structure of a sketch already in place.

Open

Allows to load a sketch file browsing through the computer drives and folders.

Open Recent

Provides a short list of the most recent sketches, ready to be opened.

Sketchbook

Shows the current sketches within the sketchbook folder structure; clicking on any name opens the corresponding sketch in a new editor instance.

Examples

Any example provided by the ESP32 Software (IDE) or library shows up in this menu item. All the examples are structured in a tree that allows easy access by topic or library.

Close

Closes the instance of the ESP32 Software from which it is clicked.

Save

Saves the sketch with the current name. If the file hasn't been named before, a name will be provided in a "Save as.." window.

Save as...

Allows to save the current sketch with a different name.

Page Setup

It shows the Page Setup window for printing.

Print

Sends the current sketch to the printer according to the settings defined in Page Setup.

Preferences

Opens the Preferences window where some settings of the IDE may be customized, as the language of the IDE interface.

Quit

Closes all IDE windows. The same sketches open when Quit was chosen will be automatically reopened the next time you start the IDE.

Edit

Undo/Redo

Goes back of one or more steps you did while editing; when you go back, you may go forward with Redo.

Cut

Removes the selected text from the editor and places it into the clipboard.

Copy

Duplicates the selected text in the editor and places it into the clipboard.

Copy for Forum

Copies the code of your sketch to the clipboard in a form suitable for posting to the forum, complete with syntax coloring.

Copy as HTML

Copies the code of your sketch to the clipboard as HTML, suitable for embedding in web pages.

Paste

Puts the contents of the clipboard at the cursor position, in the editor.

Select All

Selects and highlights the whole content of the editor.

Comment/Uncomment

Puts or removes the // comment marker at the beginning of each selected line.

Increase/Decrease Indent

Adds or subtracts a space at the beginning of each selected line, moving the text one space on the right or eliminating a space at the beginning.

Find

Opens the Find and Replace window where you can specify text to search inside the current sketch according to several options.

Find Next

Highlights the next occurrence - if any - of the string specified as the search item in the Find window, relative to the cursor position.

Find Previous

Highlights the previous occurrence - if any - of the string specified as the search item in the Find window relative to the cursor position.

Sketch

Verify/Compile

Checks your sketch for errors compiling it; it will report memory usage for code and variables in the console area.

Upload

Compiles and loads the binary file onto the configured board through the configured Port.

Upload Using Programmer

This will overwrite the bootloader on the board; you will need to use Tools > Burn Bootloader to restore it and be able to Upload to USB serial port again. However, it allows you to use the full capacity of the Flash memory for your sketch. Please note that this command will NOT burn the fuses. To do so a *Tools -> Burn Bootloader* command must be executed.

Export Compiled Binary

Saves a .hex file that may be kept as archive or sent to the board using other tools.

Show Sketch Folder

Opens the current sketch folder.

Include Library

Adds a library to your sketch by inserting #include statements at the start of your code. For more details, see libraries below. Additionally, from this menu item you can access the Library Manager and import new libraries from .zip files.

Add File...

Adds a source file to the sketch (it will be copied from its current location). The new file appears in a new tab in the sketch window. Files can be removed from the sketch using the tab menu accessible clicking on the small triangle icon below the serial monitor one on the right side of the toolbar.

Tools

Auto Format

This formats your code nicely: i.e. indents it so that opening and closing curly braces line up, and that the statements inside curly braces are indented more.

Archive Sketch

Archives a copy of the current sketch in .zip format. The archive is placed in the same directory as the sketch.

Fix Encoding & Reload

Fixes possible discrepancies between the editor char map encoding and other operating systems char maps.

Serial Monitor

Opens the serial monitor window and initiates the exchange of data with any connected board on the currently selected Port. This usually resets the board, if the board supports Reset over serial port opening.

Board

Select the board that you're using. See below for descriptions of the various boards.

Port

This menu contains all the serial devices (real or virtual) on your machine. It should automatically refresh every time you open the top-level tools menu.

Programmer

For selecting a hardware programmer when programming a board or chip and not using the onboard USB-serial connection. Normally you won't need this, but if you're burning a bootloader to a new microcontroller, you will use this.

Burn Bootloader

The items in this menu allow you to burn a bootloader onto the microcontroller on an ESP32 board.

This is not required for normal use of an ESP32 or Genuino board but is useful if you purchase a new ATmega microcontroller (which normally come without a bootloader). Ensure that you've selected the correct board from the Boards menu before burning the bootloader on the target board. This command also set the right fuses.

Help

Here you find easy access to a number of documents that come with the ESP32 Software (IDE). You have access to Getting Started, Reference, this guide to the IDE and other documents locally, without an internet connection. The documents are a local copy of the online ones and may link back to our online website.

Find in Reference

This is the only interactive function of the Help menu: it directly selects the relevant page in the local copy of the Reference for the function or command under the cursor.

Sketchbook

The ESP32 Software (IDE) uses the concept of a sketchbook: a standard place to store your programs (or sketches). The sketches in your sketchbook can be opened from the File > Sketchbook menu or from the Open button on the toolbar. The first time you run the ESP32 software, it will automatically create a directory for your sketchbook. You can view or change the location of the sketchbook location from with the Preferences dialog.

Beginning with version 1.0, files are saved with a .ino file extension. Previous versions use the .pde extension. You may still open .pde named files in version 1.0 and later, the software will automatically rename the extension to .ino.

Tabs, Multiple Files, and Compilation

Allows you to manage sketches with more than one file (each of which appears in its own tab). These can be normal ESP32 code files (no visible extension), C files (.c extension), C++ files (.cpp), or header files (.h).

Uploading

Before uploading your sketch, you need to select the correct items from the Tools > Board and Tools > Port menus. The boards are described below. On the Mac, the serial port is probably something like /dev/tty.usbmodem241 (for an Uno or Mega2560 or Leonardo) or /dev/tty.usbserial-1B1 (for a Duemilanove or earlier USB board), or /dev/tty.USA19QW1b1P1.1 (for a serial board connected with a Keyspan USB-to-Serial adapter). On Windows, it's probably COM1 or COM2 (for a serial board) or COM4, COM5, COM7, or higher (for a USB board) - to find out, you look for USB serial device in the ports section of the Windows Device Manager. On Linux, it should be /dev/ttyACMx , /dev/ttyUSBx or similar. Once you've selected the correct serial port and board, press the upload button in the toolbar or select the Upload item from the Sketch menu. Current ESP32 boards will reset automatically and begin the upload. With older boards (pre-Diecimila) that lack auto-reset, you'll need to press the reset button on the board just before starting the upload. On most boards, you'll see the RX and TX LEDs blink as the sketch is uploaded. The ESP32 Software (IDE) will display a message when the upload is complete, or show an error.

When you upload a sketch, you're using the ESP32 bootloader, a small program that has been loaded on to the microcontroller on your board. It allows you to upload code without using any additional hardware. The bootloader is active for a few seconds when the board resets; then it starts whichever sketch was most recently uploaded to the microcontroller. The bootloader will blink the on-board (pin 13) LED when it starts (i.e. when the board resets).

Libraries

Libraries provide extra functionality for use in sketches, e.g. working with hardware or manipulating data.

To use a library in a sketch, select it from the Sketch > Import Library menu. This will insert one or more #include statements at the top of the sketch and compile the library with your sketch. Because libraries are uploaded to the board with your sketch, they increase the amount of space it takes up. If a sketch no longer needs a library, simply delete its #include statements from the top of your code.

There is a list of libraries in the reference. Some libraries are included with the ESP32 software. Others can be downloaded from a variety of sources or through the Library Manager. Starting with version 1.0.5 of the IDE, you do can import a library from a zip file and use it in an open sketch. See these instructions for installing a third-party library.

To write your own library, see this tutorial.

Third-Party Hardware

Support for third-party hardware can be added to the hardware directory of your sketchbook directory. Platforms installed there may include board definitions (which appear in the board menu), core libraries, bootloaders, and programmer definitions. To install, create the hardware directory, then unzip the third-party platform into its own sub-directory. (Don't use "ESP32" as the sub-directory name or you'll override the built-in ESP32 platform.) To uninstall, simply delete its directory.

For details on creating packages for third-party hardware, see the ESP32 IDE 1.5 3rd party Hardware specification.

Serial Monitor

This displays serial sent from the ESP32 or Genuino board over USB or serial connector. To send data to the board, enter text and click on the "send" button or press enter. Choose the baud rate from the drop-down menu that matches the rate passed to `Serial.begin` in your sketch. Note that on Windows, Mac or Linux the board will reset (it will rerun your sketch) when you connect with the serial monitor. Please note that the Serial Monitor does not process control characters; if your sketch needs a complete management of the serial communication with control characters, you can use an external terminal program and connect it to the COM port assigned to your ESP32 board.

You can also talk to the board from Processing, Flash, MaxMSP, etc (see the interfacing page for details).

Preferences

Some preferences can be set in the preferences dialog (found under the ESP32 menu on the Mac, or File on Windows and Linux). The rest can be found in the preferences file, whose location is shown in the preference dialog.

Language Support

Figure 16- Language Library Of ESP32 IDE Software

Since version 1.0.1 , the ESP32 Software (IDE) has been translated into 30+ different languages. By default, the IDE loads in the language selected by your operating system. (Note: on Windows and possibly Linux, this is determined by the locale setting which controls currency and date formats, not by the language the operating system is displayed in.)

If you would like to change the language manually, start the ESP32 Software (IDE) and open the Preferences window. Next to the Editor Language there is a dropdown menu of currently supported languages. Select your preferred language from the menu, and restart the software to use the selected language. If your operating system language is not supported, the ESP32 Software (IDE) will default to English.

You can return the software to its default setting of selecting its language based on your operating system by selecting System Default from the Editor Language drop-down. This setting will take effect when you restart the ESP32 Software (IDE). Similarly, after changing your operating system's settings, you must restart the ESP32 Software (IDE) to update it to the new default language

Boards

The board selection has two effects: it sets the parameters (e.g. CPU speed and baud rate) used when compiling and uploading sketches; and sets and the file and fuse settings used by the burn bootloader command. Some of the board definitions differ only in the latter, so even if you've been uploading successfully with a particular selection you'll want to check it before burning the bootloader. You can find a comparison table between the various boards here.

ESP32 Software (IDE) includes the built in support for the boards in the following list, all based on the AVR Core. The Boards Manager included in the standard installation allows to add support for the growing number of new boards based on different cores like ESP32 Due, ESP32 Zero, Edison, Galileo and so on.

CLOUD PLATFORM

THINGSPEAK

ThingSpeak is an IoT analytics platform service that allows you to aggregate, visualize and analyze live data streams in the cloud. ThingSpeak provides instant visualizations of data posted by your devices to ThingSpeak. With the ability to execute MATLAB® code in ThingSpeak you can perform online analysis and processing of the data as it comes in. Some of the key capabilities of ThingSpeak include the ability to:

- Easily configure devices to send data to ThingSpeak using popular IoT protocols.
- Visualize your sensor data in real-time.
- Aggregate data on-demand from third-party sources.
- Use the power of MATLAB to make sense of your IoT data.
- Run your IoT analytics automatically based on schedules or events.
- Prototype and build IoT systems without setting up servers or developing web software.
- Automatically act on your data and communicate using third-party services like Twilio or Twitter.

Figure 17 – Working Of Thinspeak Cloud Platform

Send sensor data to the cloud.

There are sensors all around—in our homes, smart phones, automobiles, city infrastructure, and industrial equipment. Sensors detect and measure information on all sorts of things like temperature, humidity, and pressure. And they communicate that data in some form, such as a numerical value or electrical signal.

Why would you want to collect data in ThingSpeak?

Sensors, or things, sense data and typically act locally. ThingSpeak enables sensors, instruments, and websites to send data to the cloud to store in a channel. Once data is in a ThingSpeak channel, you can analyze and visualize it, calculate new data, or interact with social media, web services, and other devices.

Figure 18- Temperature Data On Cloud Platform

Why would you want to analyse and visualize data in Thing Speak?

Thing Speak provides access to help you make sense of data. You can:

- Convert, combine, and calculate new data.
- Schedule calculations to run at certain times.
- Visually understand relationships in data using built-in plotting functions.
- Combine data from multiple channels to build a more sophisticated analysis.

Why would you want to use ThingSpeak to act on data?

ThingSpeak provides tools that enable device communication for all of these actions and more. You can:

- React to data—both raw data and new data that you calculate—as it comes into a channel.
- Queue up commands for a device to execute.

Figure 19- Creating Fields On Thingspeak Cloud

Creating Thing Speak Account

The first thing you need to do is to create an account with ThingSpeak. Since the collaboration with MATLAB, you can use your MathWorks credentials to login to ThingSpeak using the Sign In link from this page: **THINGSPEAK**

If you do not have one, you need to create an account with MathWorks and login to ThingSpeak Application.

NOTE: The MathWorks Account can be used for both MATLAB as well as ThingSpeak logins. **Step 1: Sign up ThingSpeak** Its simple just enter your email id and verify your account

Step 2: Configuring ThingSpeak

Configuration is just few clicks job

Step 2.1: Create New Channel Click on New Channel

Figure 20 – Creating Channel On Thingspeak

Enter Name and Field. You may have multiple Fields depending on number of sensor create multiple fields such as Light, Temperature, Humidity, etc.

Figure 21- Naming Of Fields On Thingspeak

Keep everything else as it is. Blank or default values. and click on Save Channel.

Figure 22 – Saving Channel

Step 2.2: Getting API Key

Click on API Key Tab and look for these two fields Write Api Key and Update channel feed line.

Figure 23 – Getting API Key

This line is important for data upload to cloud server

After logging in, you need to create a new channel for the data to be stored. For this go to Channels->My Channels and click on New Channel.

Figure 24 – Channels In Thingspeak Account

Enter the name of the channel and name of Field 1 in the corresponding sections. Fields in a channel are used to hold the data and each channel can have up to 8 fields. After entering the details save the channel.

In my case, I've created a Channel called "Test Channel" and the Field 1 as "Random Number". You will see why in the later sections.

Figure 25 – Test Channels

There are a few other things you need to do in the ThingSpeak Application, but I'll tell about it when you need it.

Figure 26 – Data On Created Channel

Write API Key

Key:

Read API Keys

Key:

Note:

Figure 27 - Write And Read ApiKeys

Programming :

```
#include <WiFi.h>
```

```
#include <DHT.h>
```

```
#define DHTPIN 2 // Digital pin connected to the DHT sensor
```

```
#define DHTTYPE DHT11 // DHT 11
```

```
DHT dht(DHTPIN, DHTTYPE);
```

```
const char* ssid = "YourWiFiSSID";
```

```
const char* password =
```

```
"YourWiFiPassword"; const char*
```

```
server = "api.thingspeak.com"; const
```

```
String apiKey = "YourAPIKey";
```

```
const long updateInterval = 30000; // Update every 30 seconds
```

```

        void setup() {
            Serial.begin(115200);

            dht.begin();

            connectToWiFi();

        }

        void loop() {

            float humidity = dht.readHumidity();

            float temperature =

            dht.readTemperature();

int soilMoisture = analogRead(A0); // Assuming soil moisture sensor is connected to A0

            if (isnan(humidity) || isnan(temperature)) {
                Serial.println("Failed to read from DHT sensor!");

                return;

            }

            Serial.print("Temperature: ");

            Serial.print(temperature);

            Serial.print(" °C\tHumidity: ");

            Serial.print(humidity);

            Serial.print(" %\tSoil Moisture: ");

            Serial.println(soilMoisture);

```

```

        if (WiFi.status() == WL_CONNECTED) {
            sendToThingSpeak(temperature, humidity, soilMoisture);
        }

        delay(updateInterval);
    }

    void connectToWiFi() {
        Serial.print("Connecting to ");
        Serial.println(ssid);

        WiFi.begin(ssid, password);

        while (WiFi.status() != WL_CONNECTED) {
            delay(1000);
            Serial.println("Connecting to WiFi...");
        }
    }

    void sendToThingSpeak(float temperature, float humidity, int soilMoisture) {
        WiFiClient client;
        if (!client.connect(server,
            80)) {
            Serial.println("Connection to ThingSpeak failed");
            return;
        }
    }

```

```

String postStr = apiKey;

postStr += "&field1=";

    postStr +=

String(temperature);

postStr += "&field2=";

    postStr +=

String(humidity); postStr

+= "&field3="; postStr

+= String(soilMoisture);

client.print("POST /update

HTTP/1.1\n"); client.print("Host:

api.thingspeak.com\n");

client.print("Connection: close\n");

client.print("X-THINGSPEAKAPIKEY: " + apiKey + "\n");

client.print("Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded\n");

client.print("Content-Length: ");

client.print(postStr.length());

    client.print("\n\n");

    client.print(postStr);

Serial.println("Data sent to

ThingSpeak");

    }

```

PCB designing:

Eagle (Easily Applicable Graphical Layout Editor)

The EAGLE is an editor, which is easy-to-use, yet powerful tool for designing printed circuit boards (PCBs). It is a complete platform for the development of any type of complicated & sophisticated multilayered PCBs. This software consists of the following tools...

Schematic Editor

In this one can develop & design circuits for the required PCB.

Layout Editor

In this one can develop & design actual PCB structure required. This is done automatically by the software using the circuit in the schematic editor itself.

Library Editor

This is very useful in case of customized component design that does not occur in the predefined library according to our need.

Auto Router

This is an artificial intelligence based tool or subroutine that can do auto routing of the PCB tracks designed.

Cam Processor

This is used to finally print the various layers of the designed PCB viz. Top Layer, Bottom Layer, Component Layer, Masking Layer etc.

Implement of the PCB making

To make the Printed Circuit Board, following implement becomes necessary.

The way of making the Printed Circuit Board is not only the way of introducing this time.

Implement and material to use

Positive exposure printed board	<p>The material which the ultraviolet rays change the nature to has been painted the copper foil of the PCB.</p> <p>It piles the film which pictured the mask pattern on the positive exposure printed board and it irradiates the ultraviolet rays. The part where the ultraviolet rays were irradiated changes in the quality.</p> <p>When putting the positive exposure printed board which finished irradiating the ultraviolet rays in the developer, the part where the ultraviolet rays were irradiated dissolves in the developer and the masked part doesn't dissolve. The part which wasn't dissolved in the developer is left as the mask pattern of the etching and doesn't dissolve in the etchant, too.</p>
Development medicine of a sensitizer	It dissolves the sensitizer in the part where the ultraviolet rays of the positive exposure printed board were irradiated.
Mask pattern	<p>It may picture the mask pattern in the black ink at the transparent sheet.</p> <p>In the case of me, I picture the mask pattern drawing by the software, "Visio", and am using it for the overhead projector (OHP) sheet, printing.</p>
Ultraviolet ray exposure equipment	It is made even if it uses the fluorescence light desk stand. Because about 20 minutes of the light were necessary, I made the ultraviolet ray exposure equipment with the timer (the fluorescence light with the timer).
Clamp	It is the implement to hold for board and the mask pattern to stick when irradiating the ultraviolet rays to the positive exposure printed board with the ultraviolet ray exposure equipment.
Resist pen	It uses for the repair of the mask pattern. It is a kind of the oily dry ink.
Etching apparatus	<p>It is the equipment to dissolve the copper(Etching) which the printed board is unnecessary to.</p> <p>Even if there is not such equipment, the etchant can be dissolved</p>
	by putting it in the palette to use for the development of the photograph, too.

Quartz pipe heater	It is the heater which raises the temperature of the etchant at 40-43 degC. In the liquid temperature, when high, the copper melts early. It says that it must not raise at equal to or more than 45 degC.
Etching liquid	It is the solution which dissolves the copper. It is the solution of the Ferric Chloride.
Resist solvent	It uses to remove the mask pattern of the printed board that the etching was ended.
Battery style mini drill	It makes a hole which lets through the lead line of the part. The hand drill is good but I am using the mini drill of the electric formula because the bits of the drill is thin and it is easy to break.
Flux	It paints to prevent the copper of the printed board from the oxidation.
Solder resist	It paints the wiring surface of the printed board and extra solder makes not be stuck.

Table 4- Implement and material to use

Layout

Figure 28 – Layout Of PCB

Chapter-6

Result and Application

Results

The Output of Different Sensors is Shown Below. These reading shown on Laptop. But We Can Monitor easily these parameters on Cell Phone. All internet GPRS supported cell phones can show these graphical readings on thingspeak.

Figure 29- All Sensors Readings Graphical Representation on Thingspeak

Figure 30- Access Readings of Sensors from Cell Phone

Applications-

1. Agricultural monitoring
2. Green house
3. Earthing System
4. Applicable for Various Electrical Machines For Monitoring Their Data
5. Can Be Used In Plant Nurseries

Chapter - 7

Conclusion and Future scope Future

Conclusion

We as a group had begun working for more than a year ago and now we come to the completion of our project. It has been a very fulfilling experience for all of us. We have got a thorough learning experience and we shall cherish it for long. Despite being challenging and different from other assignments, it is a path where we have learnt a lot about hardware, software, troubleshooting and other aspects of engineering. It was a chance given to us that we go deep into applying what we had learnt in earlier years of our studies and we grabbed it with both hands.

For simplicity we divided the project work into smaller parts and alternately took leads in performing those parts following the principle of the best man for the job. Since we were new to this, at initial stages most of our decisions were not apt for the required situations. At such times our professors and other knowledgeable friends came to our help. From finding the project idea to publishing this report, learning has been a continuous process. There have been times where we have taken inappropriate decisions but have then learnt how to overcome them and not to commit those errors in future tasks

the IoT-based smart agriculture monitoring system offers a practical and effective solution for farmers to monitor and optimize the growth of their crops. By collecting and analyzing data on various environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and light intensity, the system provides farmers with valuable insights into the health and growth of their crops. Through the use of sensors, the system can detect potential problems such as pests, diseases, and nutrient deficiencies, allowing farmers to take prompt action to prevent or mitigate these issues. The system also enables farmers to automate various tasks such as irrigation and fertilization, saving time and resources while improving crop yields.

Looking to the future, there is great potential for further advancements in smart agriculture technology. For example, integrating artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms could improve the accuracy of data analysis and prediction of crop growth and yield. Additionally, incorporating drone technology for aerial monitoring of crops could provide even more detailed insights into crop health and growth.

Future Scope

In terms of recommendations, it is important for further research and development to focus on making smart agriculture technology more accessible and affordable for small-scale farmers who may not have the resources to invest in expensive equipment. Additionally, efforts should be made to address any potential privacy and security concerns related to the collection and storage of sensitive agricultural data. Overall, the IoT-based smart agriculture monitoring system has the potential to revolutionize the way we approach farming and food production, offering a more sustainable, efficient, and profitable approach to agriculture

- **Integration with IoT:** As the Internet of Things (IoT) continues to grow, it is likely that soil moisture sensors for earthing systems will be integrated with IoT platforms. This will enable real-time monitoring and management of earthing systems from remote locations, improving system reliability and efficiency.
- **Use of AI and Machine Learning:** The use of AI and machine learning algorithms to analyze soil moisture, temperature, humidity, data can help to optimize the design and implementation of systems. By identifying patterns and trends in the data, these algorithms can help to predict potential problems before they occur, improving system reliability and efficiency.
- **Development of Smart Agricultural Systems:** The integration of soil moisture sensors with other smart technologies, such as smart grid systems and renewable energy sources, can help to create smarter, more efficient systems that can adapt to changing environmental conditions and energy demands.
- **Improved Environmental Monitoring:** Soil moisture sensors can be used not only to optimize the system design and implementation but also to monitor the health of the soil and surrounding environment. By

analyzing soil moisture data over time, it may be possible to identify trends and patterns that can help to inform environmental management and conservation efforts.

Advantages-

1. Measurements are always taken at the right time. Unlike a human, monitoring system will not forget to take a reading or take a reading too late or too early.
2. Mistakes are not made in reading the results.
3. Data can be accessed over internet.
4. Graphs and tables of results can be produced automatically by the online API on computers.
5. Data controlling facility available.
6. Online API can be made public or private.
7. Data can be tweeted over internet in regular time intervals.
9. Data could be viewed all over the world by multiple users.
10. More fields can be added to log more parameters.
11. CSV file of logged data can be exported offline to print a record.
12. Flexibility of accessing data from different platforms i.e mobile phone, tablet, desktop, etc.

Problems Faced During Making of Project

- Bad solder joints on evaluation board.
- Appropriate drivers for USB-UART bridge.
- Making default baud rate of ESP32 as 9600.
- Library files for PCB designing.
- Bad solder joints on evaluation board.
- Appropriate drivers for USB-UART bridge.
- Making default baud rate of ESP32 as 9600.
- Library files for PCB designing

Component List

SR. No	Description
1	Adapter
2	Diode 1N4007
3	Capacitor 1000uF, 25V
4	Voltage regulator IC 2576
5	Capacitor 1uF
6	LED
7	Resistors
8	IC Base
9	PCB
10	Wires
11	Solder wire
12	Cabinet
13	Mains cord
14	Transistor BC547
15	Sensor soil
16	ESP 32
17	DHT SENSOR
18	Buzzer
19	Plywood

Table 5 – Components list

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